

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF DESIGNING MATERIALS TO TEACH VOCABULARY

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Abstract

Vocabulary is an integral language aspect to generally enhance all language skills. While teaching vocabulary, teachers are obligated to design useful and effective teaching materials as well as choose effective sources to conduct vocabulary lessons successfully. The aim of this paper is to clarify what important principles should be taken into consideration to design teaching materials for vocabulary and accentuate their significance in teaching vocabulary.

Key words : *vocabulary, approach, multimedia, principles, frequency, podcast.*

Introduction

Vocabulary plays a critical role in the learning and teaching of a second language, providing learners with the ability to communicate through various mediums such as literature, music, and knowledge. Word knowledge is essential for learning, as words are fundamental building blocks. While vocabulary building often happens through reading, in the foreign language classroom, the complexity of reading a second language makes it difficult for students to acquire the necessary vocabulary to understand texts.

Therefore, teachers must help students learn new words and provide strategies for expanding their vocabulary. Language instruction consists of five key elements: students, a teacher, teaching materials, teaching methods, and evaluation. The purpose of teaching materials is to aid students in learning and participate in classroom activities. These materials should be beneficial for both the teacher and the students, tailored to the specific content being taught, the students in the class, and the teacher's preferences. Teaching materials come in various forms but all serve to support student learning and enhance their success. Therefore, effective teaching relies on high-quality instructional materials that teachers must skillfully utilize. These materials can include textbooks, teacher-made resources, supplementary activities, handouts, charts, and review sheets.

Methods

Currently, many linguists are making efforts to develop teaching materials for the new generation. In the initial phase of creating these materials, researchers gathered and analyzed information from contemporary scientific articles that discuss the challenges in developing teaching aids. These articles emphasize the key requirements that need to be taken into account during the creation process. As these principles are the key to the success of EFL classes, teachers should be aware of them to teach vocabulary efficiently and straightforwardly.

Vocabulary knowledge is considered crucial for students to effectively communicate. The lack of vocabulary can lead to communication breakdowns, which is a challenge for many non-native students. Despite this, Uzbek students struggle with learning vocabulary, as they are limited to textbook and workbook resources in their English learning environment. This limits their exposure to authentic materials and hinders their vocabulary acquisition.

One of those prominent approaches to teaching vocabulary is using multimedia in ESL classes and material designing. In other words, this general view implies a common use of words, sound, and images. Vocabulary refers to printed or verbal texts, images include both still and dynamic graphics, video, photos, maps, and illustrations while sound includes aural input provided via radio, television, films, podcasts, and music. The proponents of the approach stress that visuality of the material can attract learners and provide intriguing learning experience.

Duquette, Renie and Laurier believe using multimedia in teaching can help students learn vocabulary more quickly and remember it better, especially when words are shown in different contexts such as animated images and images accompanied by text. Akbulut, Nikolova[1] support the idea that when words are paired with visuals, it provides additional cues for the brain to encode information, improving the learner's ability to recall it later. Studies have shown that combining text with visuals is more effective for vocabulary learning than simply providing word definitions. Multimedia also allows students to choose between visual or verbal modes, catering to individual learning styles. Additionally, learners with strong spatial abilities tend to benefit more from multimedia compared to those with weaker spatial abilities.

One effective method of incorporating multimedia into language instruction involves utilizing PowerPoint and Apple Keynote. Students can develop presentations that synthesize information from a text, using images, text, and sound to enhance their understanding. This approach creates a multi-sensory learning experience. Teachers can also utilize culturally relevant images and native pronunciations of vocabulary words in their presentations, which can be

shared on school websites for students to access and practice with. Nemtschinova[9] considers that learners make a presentation related to reading and information gained from a text and then process this information by summarizing and comprehending it through pictures, texts, and sound, thereby providing a multisensory learning environment.

Cyberbuch is a multimedia program that can be purchased, designed to enhance advanced reading skills and help learners understand vocabulary through various methods. The program offers authentic literary texts and allows students to choose how they receive information based on their preferred learning style.

Zoghi, Moradiyan, and Kazemi conducted a study on the impact of authentic materials on vocabulary growth among 50 randomly selected IELTS students. They observed multiple IELTS classes and administered a self-reported questionnaire to all students in the selected classes. The results showed that most students expressed a preference for using authentic materials to improve their vocabulary. They found that working with authentic materials allowed students to engage with real-world content, sparked their interest in real language usage, helped them become more acquainted with the culture associated with the target language, and boosted their motivation to learn a second language.

Another principle, stemming from the second one, pertains to collocation. An important teaching principle is that collocation should be introduced early on in language learning. This principle challenges the common belief that collocation is a skill reserved for more advanced stages of language acquisition. Research shows that collocation plays a role across all levels of vocabulary frequency, from common words to rare ones. Therefore, it is inaccurate to only associate collocation with less frequently used words.

An important consideration in teaching vocabulary is determining which words to focus on for learning. While some studies have suggested a personalized approach to word selection using student-chosen materials, the process of selecting words remains a significant issue for educators and researchers. Laufer and Nation[6] suggest that criteria for selecting vocabulary should include frequency, utility, and level of difficulty. While selecting words to teach language learners, there are a few aspects to consider, such as frequency, usefulness, learnability or difficulty,

Research and result

Rodengam[10] conducted a study to explore how using authentic materials can improve students' vocabulary for listening comprehension and their attitudes towards learning English vocabulary for listening comprehension. The study involved 45 high school students enrolled in the English Japanese program at Winituksa School in Thailand. The findings revealed that incorporating authentic materials had a beneficial impact on students' listening performance, comfort levels, and self-confidence in the target language. Questionnaire responses indicated that using authentic materials also positively influenced students' attitudes and motivation towards language learning. The results suggested that educators could foster a positive learning environment by providing materials and activities that cater to students' needs.

Contrary to the findings of Clark [2], who argued that media had no impact on learning regardless of authenticity, our study revealed a different outcome. Similarly, Kienbaum et al. observed no significant variations in language proficiency among children using authentic materials compared to those in a conventional classroom setting.

Criado discovered that a significant number of word types, specifically 1,873 out of 3,225 (58%), appeared only once or twice. Similarly, Norberg and Nordlund found similar results in their study of seven EFL teaching materials in Sweden, where an average of 62% of all lexical verbs, adjectives, and nouns were used no more than twice.

Discussion

Although studies have demonstrated that the 2,000-3,000 most common words are essential for establishing a strong base for expanding vocabulary, according to Schmitt[11], the vocabulary found in textbooks designed for young learners is often not aligned with everyday language usage.

In essence, high-frequency words are words that are commonly found in both spoken and written language, regardless of the situation. It is crucial for language learners to have a good understanding and be able to use these words fluently in order to improve their comprehension and communication skills. As such, focusing on teaching and learning these high-frequency words is important, especially for beginners in the language learning process.

Laufer and Nation[6] emphasized the importance of considering usefulness as a key factor in selecting words for language learning. Since nonnative speakers may have a smaller vocabulary than native speakers, it is crucial to choose words that are practical and essential for communication in the target language.

It has been proposed that textbooks can aid in vocabulary acquisition through various means, such as offering definitions. Webb and Nation contend that providing glosses helps learners notice and learn new words. Studies on vocabulary acquisition through reading have shown that using glosses during reading can result in greater vocabulary improvement compared to reading without them.

The textbook plays a crucial role in the EFL classroom, being frequently utilized by teachers and serving as a primary source of information for students. It is expected that students will acquire numerous high and mid-frequency words throughout their academic journey, and schools have a responsibility to offer ample learning opportunities. Thus, the textbook, along with supplementary vocabulary exercises, should offer a range of vocabulary input to aid in students' vocabulary growth. It is logical to suggest that teaching resources should be informed by research on factors like word frequency and repetition.

Hulstijn[4] states that while list learning is considered ineffective in current language teaching practices, its benefits have been emphasized by various studies. Despite research showing that word lists are highly efficient for rapid vocabulary acquisition and long-term retention, it is notable that developers continue to overlook the potential of word lists as effective vocabulary tools.

Conclusion

In conclusion, vocabulary teaching is a complex process and one of important considerations is designing teaching materials to enhance learners' vocabulary. While designing them, there are some essential principles to consider. This article has discussed importance of selection of words according to frequency, usefulness, authentic materials in designing vocabulary materials. It also highlights essence of inclusion of multimedia materials in material designing for vocabulary.

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